

Polarographic Studies on the Influence of the Nature and Concentration of some Supporting Electrolytes on the Diffusion Current and Half-wave Potential of Cd^{2+} and Zn^{2+} Ions. Part V

Amar Nath and Abani K. Bhattacharya

The variations in diffusion current (i_d) and half-wave potential ($E_{1/2}$) for Cd^{2+} and Zn^{2+} ions in presence of MgSO_4 , $\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, BaCl_2 , and CaCl_2 as supporting electrolytes have been determined at different concentrations. The concentration of the supporting electrolyte has been found to vary from low to high concentration; there is a fall in i_d and the interfacial tension (σ) at the mercury-solution interface. The phenomenon of adsorption at the mercury-solution interface is one of the parameters to cause deviations in i_d and $E_{1/2}$, when the concentration of the supporting electrolyte is changed.

In our previous communications¹⁻³, Ilkovic's equation was shown to be dependent on many factors, not adequately investigated so far, although it had been suggested by previous workers⁴⁻⁷ that the variations in i_d and $E_{1/2}$ were influenced by such factors as ionic strength, complex formation, viscosity, overvoltage, interionic attraction, and by other factors as well, depending on the nature and concentration of the supporting electrolytes. On the basis of our experimental observations¹⁻³, the order of decrease in i_d of reducible Cd^{2+} ions was more or less in conformity with the fall in interfacial tension of the system at the mercury-liquid surface with increasing concentration of the supporting inorganic electrolytes. On the contrary, in the case of another series, such as oxalates, tartrates and citrates of Na, K, and NH_4 , the above relation was found to be anomalous.³

The decrease in the interfacial tension at the mercury-liquid interface with increasing concentration of the supporting electrolytes, such as chloride, bromide, iodide, nitrate, sulphate, isothiocyanate, and acetate containing mono and bivalent cations of Na, K, NH_4 , Ca, Ba, Sr, Zn, and Mg, significantly suggested the role of adsorption in varying i_d and $E_{1/2}$, but the anomaly observed in the case of oxalates, tartrates, and citrates might be ascribed to some other factors which play a greater role than adsorption at the mercury-drop surface. The viscosity changes of these supporting electrolytes were found to be very much greater by increasing their concentration than that of the chlorides, bromides, nitrates, etc. of the former series. But, since $i_d \times \eta^{1/2}$ was not constant, it was presumed that the

1. Nath and Bhattacharya, this *Journal*, 1963, 40, 253.
2. *Idem*, *ibid.*, 1964, 41, 433.
3. *Idem*, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1964, 2, 419.
4. Doford and Anderson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 3918.
5. Vleck, *Chem. Listy*, 1954, 48, 1474.
6. Micka, *ibid.*, 1956, 50, 203.
7. Mukherjee and Chakravarty, this *Journal*, 1961, 38, 995; 1962, 39, 149.

tendency of these organic ions to form complexes might be responsible for the anomaly between the former and the latter series.

In this communication observations on the role of adsorption have been further extended to the reducible systems of Cd^{2+} and Zn^{2+} at different concentrations of the series, MgSO_4 , $\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, BaCl_2 , and CaCl_2 , used as supporting electrolytes. The results obtained (Tables I and II) show that i_d and σ_i decrease regularly with the concentration of the supporting electrolytes for both the reducible systems.

EXPERIMENTAL

Current-voltage measurements during the polarographic reduction of Cd^{2+} and Zn^{2+} were recorded with the help of a sensitive spot galvanometer. The saturated calomel cell used as a reference electrode was connected to the solution cell through the saturated solution of NH_4NO_3 bridge in order to nullify the effect of liquid junction potential. The concentration of CdCl_2 was $0.001M$ and of ZnCl_2 , $0.0005M$. Gelatin (0.02%) was used as a maximum suppressor. Hydrogen was bubbled to deoxygenate the solution. Drop time was maintained at 3 sec./drop.

The interfacial tensions between the mercury surface and the reducible system in presence of supporting electrolyte at different concentrations were determined by the capillary method⁸ and calculated by the relation:

$$\sigma_i = \frac{rg}{2} (h'd' - h''d'')$$

where r is the radius, d' and d'' , densities of mercury and solution, and h' and h'' , heights of mercury and solution column, respectively, above mercury-solution interface. The interfacial tensions were measured at the contact surface of mercury and supporting electrolyte solution, as stated above, without applying any potential.

TABLE I
Cd²⁺ as the reducing ion.

Cone.	i_d	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$	σ_i (dynes/cm).	ΓRT .	η (m. poise).	$\mu = \frac{1}{2} \sum CZ^2$ (ionic strength).
A. MgSO_4 .						
<i>M</i> /100	8.80 μa	0.580 volt	370.2	..	8.650	0.043
<i>M</i> /25	8.40	0.590	358.4	19.60	8.752	0.163
<i>M</i> /10	8.00	0.595	352.7	14.67	8.990	0.403
<i>M</i> /4	7.60	0.600	348.5	10.55	9.290	1.003
<i>M</i> /2	7.40	0.610	346.2	7.64	10.260	2.003
B. $\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$.						
<i>M</i> /100	8.40	0.570	368.4	..	8.590	0.033
<i>M</i> /25	8.00	0.575	356.4	19.93	8.610	0.123
<i>M</i> /10	8.20	0.580	350.1	15.84	8.632	0.303
<i>M</i> /4	7.80	0.580	347.2	7.28	8.810	0.753
<i>M</i> /2	7.80	0.580	345.3	6.31	9.730	1.503

8. Bartell *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **55**, 2419.

TABLE I (contd.)

Conc.	i_d	$E_{1/2}$	σ_1 (dynes/cm).	ΓRT	η (m. poise).	$\mu = \frac{1}{2} \sum CZ^2$ (ionic strength).
C. CaCl_2 .						
<i>M</i> /100	8.80 μa	0.580 volt	371.2	..	8.810	0.033
<i>M</i> /25	8.40	0.590	358.5	21.90	9.040	0.123
<i>M</i> /10	8.00	0.600	352.4	16.33	9.202	0.303
<i>M</i> /4	8.20	0.605	348.4	10.06	9.736	0.753
<i>M</i> /2	7.80	0.620	346.2	7.31	10.120	1.503
D. BaCl_2 .						
<i>M</i> /100	9.60	0.600	365.4	..	9.020	0.033
<i>M</i> /25	9.00	0.610	355.4	18.27	9.143	0.123
<i>M</i> /10	8.80	0.615	348.5	17.35	9.408	0.303
<i>M</i> /4	8.40	0.625	344.1	10.30	9.734	0.753
<i>M</i> /2	8.00	0.630	341.4	8.95	10.420	1.503
E. $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$.						
<i>M</i> /100	9.40	0.590	365.1	..	8.554	0.033
<i>M</i> /25	9.00	0.595	354.4	17.77	9.020	0.123
<i>M</i> /10	8.80	0.590	348.5	14.84	9.120	0.303
<i>M</i> /4	8.80	0.590	345.3	8.04	9.204	0.753

TABLE II

Zn²⁺ as the reducing ion.

Conc.	i_d	$E_{1/2}$	σ_1 (dynes/cm).	ΓRT	η (m. poise).	$\mu = \frac{1}{2} \sum CZ^2$ (ionic strength).
A. MgSO_4 .						
<i>M</i> /25	4.34 μa	1.030 volt	366.8	..	8.744	0.1615
<i>M</i> /10	4.13	1.035	359.2	20.91	8.976	0.4015
<i>M</i> /4	3.78	1.040	353.0	17.09	9.264	1.0015
<i>M</i> /2	3.50	1.050	348.9	13.62	10.182	2.0015
B. CaCl_2 .						
<i>M</i> /25	4.76	1.02	370.6	..	8.995	0.1215
<i>M</i> /10	4.34	1.03	362.3	22.89	9.122	0.3015
<i>M</i> /4	4.48	1.04	355.6	18.46	9.663	0.7515
<i>M</i> /2	3.92	1.06	350.8	15.94	10.200	1.5015
C. BaCl_2 .						
<i>M</i> /25	4.48	1.03	368.2	..	9.084	0.1215
<i>M</i> /10	4.13	1.04	360.8	20.40	9.301	0.3015
<i>M</i> /4	3.92	1.06	354.7	16.82	9.602	0.7515
<i>M</i> /2	3.85	1.07	350.0	15.61	10.330	1.5015
D. $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$.						
<i>M</i> /100	4.41	1.020	371.7	..	8.882	0.0315
<i>M</i> /25	4.34	1.020	359.7	19.93	8.984	0.1215
<i>M</i> /10	4.20	1.025	355.6	11.32	9.085	0.3015
<i>M</i> /4	4.13	1.030	352.5	8.60	9.164	0.7515

DISCUSSION

From the results in Tables I and II the values of i_d and $E_{1/2}$ appear to depend on the cation as well as on the anion of the supporting electrolytes. The diffusion current also varies with the lowering of the interfacial tension (σ_i), which means that i_d decreases when there is a positive adsorption ($d\sigma_i/dc$ being negative) at the surface of the mercury drop according to Gibbs' adsorption equation.

Since the pressure of mercury

$$P_{\text{eff.}} = \propto \frac{1}{\sigma_i} \cdot \propto \frac{1}{t},$$

drop time t would rise or fall with the interfacial tension at the surface of the mercury drop, particularly when the concentration of the supporting electrolyte varies between high and low concentrations. Thus σ_i and t are connected with the effect of the adsorption to influence the value of the i_d which has not been accounted for in Ilkovic's equation. That the value of ΓRT , recorded in the tables, can be defined from its dimensions as the rate of change of adsorption with concentration, has already been reported². Hence this quantity seems to be connected with the state of the saturation of the mercury drop with respect to the adsorbed ion. Further, the effect of adsorption and the ionic strength can be interlinked because both are functions of the concentration of supporting electrolytes.

Hammer and Lagowski⁹ suggested that the suppression of i_d in the reduction of NH_4ClO_4 with increasing concentration of the supporting electrolyte, NaClO_4 , was due to the common-ion effect and several other factors. But the observed facts indicate that the variation in the values of i_d and $E_{1/2}$ is a more general phenomenon. Evidently, the deviations of i_d and $E_{1/2}$ from Ilkovic's equation at different concentrations of the supporting electrolyte are due to adsorption of ions in many cases. $i_d \times \eta^{1/2}$ is not constant, hence the change in i_d may not be attributed to the values of η , so much as adsorption.

Due to adsorption of the anion, the mercury drop may carry a slightly greater potential than that directly applied. Thus the slight increase in the values of $E_{1/2}$ in most cases may be visualised, if this view is admissible. Further work is in progress.